

SOCIAL STATUS OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS WITH HEARING PROBLEMS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

Rakhmatova Shirin Nig'mon qizi

Teacher of the Department of Clinical Fundamentals of Surdopedagogy and Special Pedagogy of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Mirsobitova Lobar Mirziyod qizi

Student of the Surdopedagogy department of the Faculty of "Special Pedagogy and Inclusive Education" of Nizami Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

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Abstract: The article studies the normative and legal foundations of the social situation in the development of students with hearing problems in primary school, its specificity, problems of the social situation in their development and the factors influencing them.

Keywords: Social adaptation, concept of social adaptation, adaptive diagnostics, correction, social integration.

The role of educational institutions in the socialization of students with hearing problems in modern society is of decisive importance. The problems of social adaptation and rehabilitation of students with hearing problems are solved by including them in existing areas of daily individual and socially significant activity, taking into account the personal interests and capabilities of students, in the context of targeted socio-pedagogical influence.

Primary education is the initial stage of general secondary education. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, primary education includes grades 1-4 and education begins at the age of 6-7. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education No. O'RQ-637 dated 23.09.2020 states that primary education is aimed at forming the foundations of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for obtaining general secondary education. There is a curriculum and educational programs for primary education classes, and based on the curriculum, students are provided with knowledge in the following subjects: reading, native language, mathematics, fine arts, education, physical education, technology, natural science, music, English, Russian. According to the state educational standard, the number of students in primary, secondary, and high school grades of comprehensive schools should not exceed 35.

In specialized boarding schools for children with hearing problems, primary education includes grades 0-1-4. Since children with hearing problems do not have hearing, they cannot immediately start studying in the 1st grade of a specialized boarding school for children with hearing problems. Only graduates

of specialized preschool educational institutions for children with hearing problems with the relevant documents and the conclusion of a medical-pedagogical-psychological commission can be admitted to the 1st grade of a specialized boarding school for children with hearing problems. Children who do not attend specialized preschool educational institutions for children with hearing problems and who come from home to specialized boarding schools for children with hearing problems, with the appropriate documents and the conclusion of the medical-pedagogical-psychological commission, may be admitted to the 1st grade after receiving education in the preparatory class of this school for 1 academic year and adapting to the social environment of this school.

Social development is the process of students with hearing problems mastering the values, culture, traditions, and customs of the society in which they live, participating in play activities, communicating with adults and peers, learning to live side by side with others, taking into account the interests of others, the rules and norms of behavior in society, that is, social maturity. Hearing impairment significantly complicates the socialization of deaf and hard-of-hearing children, which is primarily associated with the disruption of their social contacts with the outside world due to the absence or serious underdevelopment of speech.

The childhood stage, when the foundation for successful social adaptation to society is laid, is of particular importance. The child gets acquainted with the rules of behavior, customs, and etiquette, learns the language of the people around him, that is, in the broad sense of the word, assimilates the culture of the people.

Socialization of children with hearing problems is their integration into society so that they can acquire and assimilate certain values and generally accepted norms of behavior necessary for society, apply them in independent life and provide assistance. In order for children with hearing problems to enter adulthood, it is necessary, first of all, to create pedagogical conditions for the social adaptation of children in the family and educational institutions.

The concept of socialization and social adaptation of students in the primary grades of specialized boarding schools for children with hearing problems requires the definition of this concept. But, first of all, we should pay attention to the definition of the term "socialization".

According to I.S. Kon, socialization is the assimilation by an individual of social experience, certain social roles and a system of culture, during which a social personality develops.

According to N.I. Shevandrin, "socialization" is a process and a result. That is, the process of an individual entering into social relations. Both scientists emphasize that a person, having mastered social roles and relations, becomes a person, acquires the knowledge and skills necessary in life.

Socialization is the process of assimilating certain knowledge, values, norms, attitudes, and behavioral patterns that are included in the concept of culture inherent in society as a whole to a social group. In particular, in the socialization of students with hearing impairments to the norms necessary for their successful functioning in this society, it is important to create the necessary conditions for the gradual assimilation of socially significant behavioral experiences, cultural norms of communication with other people, and moral and labor culture by students.

Social adaptation (from the Greek "adapto" - adaptation) means ensuring that the individual and group behavior of children with special educational needs corresponds to social rules and values. Social adaptation is the training of children with hearing impairments to a normal lifestyle and to use the normal conditions of an open society throughout their lives. Social adaptation is a continuous, active adaptation of an individual to the conditions of the social environment and the result of this process. Although social adaptation occurs regularly, this process is usually periodically associated with significant changes in the life and activities of the individual and those around him. The central aspect of social adaptation is the individual's acceptance of his social role. In social adaptation, a complex rehabilitation system provides the highest possible level of preparation. This process includes 3 main stages, each of which performs its own tasks:

- Adaptive diagnostics;
- Correction;
- Integration.

At the adaptive diagnostics stage, the development of the child's personality is diagnosed and the most optimal correctional and educational work with him is determined.

At the correction stage, rehabilitation work is organized and carried out with the child, and the parent or guardian is trained in rehabilitation technologies.

At the integration stage, the child's integration paths into society are determined and all complex rehabilitation work is carried out within a certain period. The purpose of this rehabilitation work is to achieve the social status, financial independence, and socio-domestic adaptation of the child with hearing impairment.

Through social rehabilitation, the specific psychological characteristics of the child with hearing impairment are developed. During the process, a number of problems associated with a large number of internal and external factors that arise in a child with hearing impairment affect the development of the child. In order to effectively start this process, it is necessary to study their specific characteristics, foresee their positive and negative aspects, the results of the impact and start correction in a timely manner.

In conclusion, ensuring that students with hearing problems in specialized boarding schools have equal opportunities with all other citizens, preventing restrictions in their life activities, creating favorable conditions that allow them to live as full members of society, actively participate in social, economic, political life, and fulfill their civic duties is the main content of the humanitarian policy of our President.

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